

Research

Color hue controlling of blue ceramic pigments with low cobalt contents via crystal field engineering

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Abstract: Ceramic pigment is the most basic chromogenic substance introduced into all ceramic coloring materials. In recent years, the development of ceramic pigments has been able to keep the quality and color stability of ceramics even after 1300 °C. Studies have proved that these ceramic pigments have good color performance under the tests of high temperature and acid and alkali resistance. In this paper, Co²⁺-doped Mg_{1-x}Al_{2-2x}Si_xO₄ was prepared by high-temperature solid-state method. The main crystal phase and its content of the synthesized pigment were studied by X-ray powder diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscope (SEM), fluorescence-spectrum (PL), diffuse reflection spectrum and precise analysis colorimeter. The crystal structure, chromaticity, acid and alkali resistance of ceramics and color rendering performance of glass of pigments doped with different amounts of Al were observed and tested. The results of XRD and Raman spectra show that MgSiO₄ is a perovskite-type ceramic pigment. The main crystalline phase of the pigment is MgSiO₄, and the secondary crystalline phase is MgAl₂O₄. Co²⁺ replaces Mg²⁺ to make the pigment yellowish brown. Impurities such as MgAl₂SiO₄ and MgAl₂O₄ will be produced when different amounts of Cu are doped at 1400 °C calcination temperature. However, at the calcination temperature of 1300 °C, the temperature will be compared, and it is not easy to produce impurities, indicating that the temperature limit is around 1300 °C. At 1400 °C, the color of the pigment becomes lighter with the increase of Al content, especially when the concentration is higher, the pigment is yellowish brown in glass. At 1300 °C, the color of the pigment has no obvious change with the increase of Al content, and the color of the pigment in the glass is yellow, and its good color rendering performance is consistent with that of the calcined sample. In the test of acid and alkali resistance of samples, hydrochloric acid (HCl) is used as the acid and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) is used as the alkali. The data obtained by the precise analysis colorimeter also shows that the corrosion resistance is good.

Keywords: ceramic, color, Co²⁺ doping, Mg_{1-x}Si_{1-x}Al_{2x}O₃, high-temperature

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Introduction

An overview of the relevant research findings in and outside China, the theoretical and practical significance of the research topic, and the relevant references.

Inorganic blue pigments such as cobalt aluminate (CoAl_2O_4) are the most common and widely used blue pigment among different kinds of blue inorganic pigments available such as Co_2SiO_4 (olivine), $(\text{Co,Zn})_2\text{SiO}_4$ (willemite) and CoAl_2O_4 (cobalt spinel). The inorganic pigment cobalt blue is known as a typical blue inorganic pigment because the Co^{2+} locates in tetrahedral position as the source of the observed blue color. This inorganic pigment has high concentrations of the ions Co^{2+} , which are common for blue inorganic pigments. We use this blue CoAl_2O_4 pigment in a range of goods including plastics, paint, glassware (including glazes and porcelain enamel), and ceramics (containing glazes and porcelain enamel). Additionally,

this inorganic CoAl_2O_4 pigment has great acid and alkali resistance, enhanced heat stability, and a range of other characteristics that contribute to its remarkable performance in a variety of applications [1,2].

The optimization of the preparation technique for commercial CoAl_2O_4 pigment has garnered a great deal of interest over the past few years, and this has prompted a significant amount of study into enhancing the efficiency with which commercial CoAl_2O_4 pigment may be produced. CoAl_2O_4 manufacturing has traditionally relied on solid-state techniques, which have been the norm in the industry for many years. The good news is that things are beginning to change in this regard. Wet-chemical techniques for the synthesis of Nano-sized CoAl_2O_4 particles have previously been shown to be superior to solid-state procedures in the manufacture of CoAl_2O_4 particles [3-5]. Wet-chemical approaches include the sol-gel technique, hydrothermal treatment, Pechini method, reverse micro-emulsion method, and combustion process, to name a few [6-12]. It is possible to deal with the challenges listed above in a timely manner as a result of the use of these solutions. These solutions are scalable and can be used throughout the solid-state manufacturing process as required. The toxicity of cobalt, as well as the availability of cobalt-containing compounds, have been called into question in the past due to the fact that cobalt is essential in the development of the blue hue of cobalt aluminum oxide (CoAl_2O_4) pigment, which is composed mostly of cobalt. The conclusion reached by various experts is that cobalt, a potentially hazardous element, has a significant environmental impact on the manufacturing process at a large-scale manufacturing facility, and that this environmental impact continues throughout the course of the manufacturing process at the large-scale manufacturing facility [7, 8]. Moreover, due to the rarity of cobalt as a natural resource, the cost of creating it would be greater due to the high cost of raw materials that would be needed in its creation. Consequently, researchers have determined that including particular alternative. Adding elements such as zinc and/or magnesium into spinel's composition has shown to be an effective technique to lowering the amount of Co^{2+} present in the material [9]. However, the increasing of the amount of zinc (Zn^{2+}) or magnesium (Mg^{2+}) ions in CoAl_2O_4 pigments led to a decrease of blue hue of the pigment. The structural and optical characteristics of the pigments. How to reduce the Co contents in the pigment while maintaining the high blue hue remains an unsolved problem. During this project, I will investigate how to synthesize a blue ceramic pigment with a low cobalt content and high blue hue by partly replacing Al^{3+} and Mg^{2+} with Si^{4+} ions to adjust the crystal field environment around Co^{2+} ions and thus the color of the pigments [13].

Objectives

The main objective of this research is to design and synthesis new blue ceramic pigments with low cobalt content. The Co^{2+} doped MgAl_2O_4 was selected as the research system. The Si^{4+} was introduced in the system by substituting the Al and Mg ions to engineering the crystal field environment of Co^{2+} and thus the blue hue of the pigments. In this work, we will carry out the following researches.

1. The synthesis of Co^{2+} and Si^{4+} co-doped MgAl_2O_4 ceramic pigments: The influence of the contents of Co^{2+} and Si^{4+} , the sintering temperatures and the sizes of the raw materials on the color hue of the pigments will be systematically studied.
2. The morphology characterization: The relationship between the grain size and morphology will be illustrated in detailed.
3. The color performance of the obtained ceramics: the color performance of the above optimized pigments will be test by applying the pigment in the glass or glaze.
4. The stability of the pigments: The chemical stability of the pigments will be evaluated by soaking in the acidic and alkaline solution according to the procedure in GB/T 5211.5-2008.

Research Methodology

Experimental procedure

Co^{2+} doped $\text{Mg}^{1+x}\text{Al}_{2-2x}\text{Si}_x\text{O}_4$ ($x=0-0.4$) ceramic pigments were prepared by a traditional high temperature solid-state reaction method. Stoichiometric amounts of MgO (A.R.), Al_2O_3 (A.R.), SiO_2 (A.R.), $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (99.99%) were thoroughly mixed via grinding in an agate mortar for 0.5 h with an appropriate amount of ethanol. The powder mixtures were then transferred into alumina crucibles and sintered in a furnace at 800 °C for 3 h. After cooling to room temperature, the samples were re-ground and then sintered at 1400 °C for 3h to obtain the final products.

Characterization

The crystal phases of the samples were identified by XRD on Persee XD-6 X-ray powder diffractometer operated at 36 kv and 20 mA with graphite-monochromatized $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda= 0.15406$ nm). The micro structure of the sample was characterized by an

SN-3400 scanning electron microscope (SEM). UV-vis diffuse reflectance spectra (DRS) were measured using a UV-vis spectrophotometer (EVOLUTION 220) with an integrating sphere under ambient conditions. The color coordinates of samples were recorded on a colorimeter HP-200. The stability of the pigments was evaluated by immersing the pigment in 2% HCl and 2% NaOH solution for 5 min.

Figure 2 the UV-vis diffusion spectra of $\text{MgAl}_2\text{Si}_6\text{O}_4:\text{Co}$ ($x=0, 0.1, \dots$)

Figure 3 XRD

The XRD patterns of $\text{MgAl}_2\text{O}_4:\text{Co}^{2+}$ with different amount of SiO_2 are presented in Figure 2. Diffraction peaks originating from spinal MgAl_2O_4 can be observed in all samples. The peak intensity of MgAl_2O_4 phase enhanced with the increase of the SiO_2 contents in the samples, suggesting that the addition of SiO_2 improved the crystallization of MgAl_2O_4 . Besides, diffraction peaks from unreacted Al_2O_3 were also observed in Si_0 sample, which became weak and diminished

with the addition of SiO₂. Moreover, diffraction peaks from SiO₂ phase were observed in all samples with SiO₂ and these peaks become eminent with the augment of SiO₂ content in the samples, suggesting that the solubility of Si⁴⁺ in MgAl₂O₄ is low. Furthermore, the diffraction peaks shifted to the larger angles with the addition of SiO₂. Considering the ionic radius of Si⁴⁺ (0.04 nm), Al³⁺(0.0535 nm) and Mg²⁺(0.072 nm), the substitution of Al³⁺-Mg²⁺ with Si⁴⁺-Si⁴⁺ will induced the shrink of the crystal lattice of MgAl₂O₄. The shift of the diffraction peaks to the longer angle after Si addition further confirmed that some Si⁴⁺ ions are incorporated into the MgAl₂O₄ crystal lattice by substituting the Al³⁺-Mg²⁺ ions.

Conclusion

Prepare sol-gel pigment precursors for hue cobalt blue. The reaction duration is 13 h with 0.01 mol/L Co²⁺ ions and 1.5 h with 0.2 mol/L Co²⁺ ions, indicating that increasing metal ion concentration benefits the fast form. Metal ions cannot form a sol when the sol reaction temperature is below 65°C. When the temperature reaches 65°C, the sol starts to form, and the gel formation period is 13.5 hours. The gel formation duration decreased to 3.5 hours at 90°C, indicating that increasing the sol reaction temperature speeds up gel formation. SEM characterisation shows that dispersant may enhance cobalt blue pigment aggregation. Glycerol dispersion is better than ethylene glycol by colorimeter. Dry gel cannot form complete spinel structure following self-propagating combustion, as shown by XRD analysis.

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